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Monopolies and Transition in Kosovo

Abstract

This study begins by acknowledging the prevailing presence of monopolies in modern economies. Simultaneously, both globally and domestically, efforts persist to curb or restrict the dominance of monopolies through the implementation of antimonopoly legislation, antimonopoly commissions, boards, committees, and similar measures. During such endeavors, their primary objective is to solicit the assistance of the government. The severity of this battle has approached levels comparable to those of a genuine military operation in Kosovo in recent months. This research aims to elucidate this phenomenon and address inquiries on the essence of monopolies in transition economies.

Keywords: Monopoly, a firm's best behavior, and the impact of state violence on the economy.

INTRODUCTION

While our economic literature may lack extensive study of present transitional trends, it is undeniable that there is a strong public interest in themes related to economic transitions. Newspapers and tabloids, although their distinctions are becoming less clear, contain sensational news regarding privatization, economic malpractices, and various criminal activities. These publications provide vivid illustrations of the lives and operations of numerous criminals involved in various sectors such as construction, energy, agriculture, trade, and transportation.

Metodologjia:

Does current technology determine the ideal size of enterprises in such a way that, in tiny markets, corporations naturally evolve into monopolies?

Can the rise of monopolies be somewhat attributed to the significant reduction in market competition in these regions (resulting from the disintegration of the state following the collapse of the Berlin Wall)?

Can the presence of monopolistic conduct in Kosovo be partially attributed to the historical practice of self-managed economics, wherein an unconscious adoption of an economic philosophy that relies on such practice occurs?

Are the negative (and also positive) aspects of the monopoly or oligopoly equilibrium of producers (supply) accurately understood?

What are the negative consequences of a monopoly market structure, and how is the concept of free competition, which is a fundamental mechanism of the market economy, understood in both our practical implementation and theoretical understanding?

The objective of the paper

Lately, there has been a significant focus on monopolies as a key factor contributing to the high pricing, inflation, and sluggish economic growth in the Kosovar economy over the past few years. This subject is not novel in our newspapers. It is worth noting that in 2004, the former director of the Economic Institute asserted that the domestic economy was not adversely affected by the opening up of international trade but rather hindered by the presence of local monopolies. "We currently possess a retail monopoly in Kosovo, which we are gradually consolidating by acquiring all the chains and retail stores across the country." A monopoly in the production of milk and milk products, a monopoly in the sugar industry, and even a monopoly in the pharmaceutical industry have all emerged. This has resulted in the formation of cartels in these industries. "The essence is that the act of opening borders has little practical significance." Monopolies hindered the liberalization of foreign trade rather than causing harm to our economy. "Monopolies have a detrimental impact on our population and standards," he stated. According to him, dismantling monopolies can be achieved using two types of tools: regulatory and market-based. He estimated that the majority of monopolistic companies effectively evade paying taxes. "None of the prominent industrialists, who proudly claim affiliations with the previous political parties, fulfill their tax obligations." As an illustration, the proportion of property tax in the overall fiscal revenue for the previous year amounted to 0.8 percent. "This is incredulous," he exclaimed. He said that monopolies should be subjected to competition by introducing another retail chain or a formidable competitor, thus fostering rivalry and driving down prices. Once a monopoly is established and the

national market is closed, development comes to a halt. Only the entity that possesses a monopoly can dictate the price, leaving no alternative options. Hence, merely liberalizing the global trade system is insufficient; it is imperative to also liberalize the domestic market.

It is important to note that despite the criticisms of the Institute, the political faction managed to establish productive relationships with the companies that were publicly accused of exploiting their dominant market position. This allowed for a harmonious collaboration between these companies and the previous as well as the current regime. However, astute observers of the intricate economic and political landscape were not oblivious to the intermittent resurgences of anti-monopoly rhetoric. This rhetoric may be strategically employed in the future, when the pursuit of "monopoly witches" becomes opportune. As eloquently proclaimed four years ago, it can serve as a means to "bring in a giant from the side." It may be advantageous, but not unprecedented, for a large and influential entity to acquire the complete infrastructure of a financially struggling monopolistic company at a reasonable cost.

Monopolies are alleged to engage in price gouging. There is a common misunderstanding in our country that a monopolist has the power to set prices as they wish, not just control the quantity of goods or services offered. This paper will further discuss the issue of high profit margins and low productivity in our commercial chains, which is a result of the absence of free competition. The identity of the "giants from abroad" who should be brought to Kosovo is clearly specified. He claims that there are no overseas retailers comparable to "Tesco," "Carrefour," or "Sainsbury's." Long-standing features are present in Poland, the Czech Republic, and Romania. We require the exchange of goods and services that are present in our banking industry and, more recently, in the field of mobile telephones. It should be acknowledged that the banking sector is not the most appropriate example in this situation, given that the real interest rates (i.e., the prices of credit) in Kosovo are exceptionally high. Moreover, the disparity between active and passive interest rates in recent years is alarming when compared to more advanced banking systems.

An unyielding battle against exorbitant prices is occurring on the Internet. We will provide an excerpt from the article titled "In Kosovo, prices surpass those in Germany," which elicited a significant number of reactions. Additionally, it includes a "distrust table" that presents a comparison of the retail pricing of various products.

However, within the fervor of the online debate, a participant expressed: "Indeed, all of this is accurate... and the circumstances are further exacerbated when considering the cost of technology, computers, and similar devices." Currently, the cost of goods and services in Kosovo is higher than in Western Europe. Furthermore, when comparing prices to those in America, the impact is even more severe due to the unfavorable exchange rate of the dollar. The perceptive participant in the online conversation failed to realize a contradiction: if the weak value of the dollar leads to lower prices in the United States, why do you not consider that the weak value of the euro might also contribute, at least partially, to lower prices in Europe, including Germany? It would be difficult to explain how the monopolist's influence on the seemingly low exchange rate of the euro, which the Bank in Kosovo enforces or protects, came about. This fact illuminates the "Table for Disbelief" from a completely different perspective.

Related conclusions on comparative analysis

Students are fatigued by the frequent inclusion of instances of natural monopolies in economics textbooks, such as diamond mines, oil resources, and the innate talents of artists or sportsmen. Nevertheless, it is crucial to bear in mind that the competition for dominance over natural monopolies (such as energy

supplies and raw materials) is the paramount feature of our current era, including both economic and political developments.

The most dominant military and economic powers are exerting significant efforts to retain their existing monopolistic position or, if feasible, to obtain monopolies in new domains. It is worth mentioning that the discourse that ensues after the competition for monopoly is consistently infused with terminology derived from liberal ideology. A dominant global power challenges the authority of another nation to control valuable natural resources that are crucial for the progress of humanity as a whole. Furthermore, it suggests that it will utilize its exclusive control over advanced weaponry to influence the allocation of these resources. In a more equitable manner, which has previously proven successful in countries without sufficient power to safeguard their territorial integrity and maintain control over natural resources, Undoubtedly, these actions are undertaken with the objective of promoting liberalization, fostering overall advancement, and facilitating the continued growth of democratic interactions among nations. The global pursuit of safeguarding freedom and competition frequently boils down to a battle for dominant military and economic supremacy, often resulting in a monopolistic position for the most powerful nations.

It exhibits similarities on a small scale. The assertion that every participant in market competition eventually strives for a monopolistic position cannot be contested, even in textbook illustrations of the free competition model. If we suppose that his objective is not to maximize profit, meaning to raise it and so capture the maximum possible market share, the producer's behavior model leading to an optimal solution (competition equilibrium) would be invalidated. However, due to the fact that all participants in the market are striving to establish a monopoly, it is unlikely that any of them will be able to accomplish this objective in the majority of industries and circumstances. As a result, a situation of free competition is naturally established, where no individual player has a significant impact on the supply level or price.

Curiously, critics of the increasing risk of monopolies in our country do not target state monopolies or monopolies held by foreign entities, be they private or state-owned. The global software conglomerate "Microsoft," whose products are ubiquitous and used by millions and billions of consumers worldwide, receives very little attention about its monopolistic status in Kosovo, particularly in comparison to the steel industry's situation. Almost indescribable.

The subject at hand is why the disparity between active and passive interest rates is so alarming in our money market, notwithstanding the presence of open competition and the dominance of foreign owners. Should we also seek out imperceptible and influential individuals in this domain—monopolists or oligopolists?

Additionally, it encompasses government control over telephone and railway communications, as well as the electric power business and specific categories of public utilities. A multitude of vociferous activists and lobbyists are fervently calling for a more comprehensive state acquisition of certain domains, such as higher education.

It is noteworthy that there is a clear inclination to consistently marginalize local owners, including the Kosovar state, in certain crucial economic sectors such as telecommunications (specifically mobile telephony), finance, and commercial distribution chains. These sectors appear to be exclusively reserved for global leaders and their capital on a global scale.

Conducting a comparative review of ownership structures in less developed countries could potentially reveal that global leaders do not permit locals to possess systems that provide the biggest profits. It

cannot be definitively said that this holds true for every underdeveloped country, but there are indeed specific signs. For certain individuals, this may appear to be an overly suspicious "conspiracy theory." Many people will perceive this as an inherent outcome of the principles of capital and capitalism, which, following the collapse of the Berlin Wall, genuinely evolved into a global phenomenon. The third point will demonstrate the necessity for the least powerful individuals to acknowledge and adhere to their exclusive control over technological expertise. Therefore, it is understandable that people who have made significant investments in research and development are reluctant to embrace the notion of knowledge being utilized as a shared resource from which anybody can profit.

Entities based in less developed nations, particularly those that are citizens of weaker states, should be especially aware of this concept. The utilization of military force (both offensive and defensive) and the influence of propaganda are not deployed in a manner that suggests an equitable and competitive conflict on the world stage. Through an advanced system of media propaganda, which includes a monopoly on media and global news, as well as the use of military force and persuasive messages from financial capital, powerful entities are able to effortlessly persuade the global public of their entitlements and legitimacy. They also undermine the rights of the less powerful to control resources within their own territories, such as energy sources, financial flow systems, large distribution chains, and, crucially, electronic media.

Indeed, international law exists with the intention of safeguarding the rights of the vulnerable. However, in the absence of strong support from any military forces, the weak are always susceptible to the powerful's demands for economic and other forms of coercion.

The problem is that the militants' instilling of fear prompts acts of terrorism (of a different kind) by the weak and the unjust, who are prepared to risk everything, including their lives, in order to overthrow the oppressive and exploitative system that degrades them. The victims of both forms of terrorism are invariably innocent civilians.

Collective economic systems proved ineffective due to their disregard for human autonomy and self-interest. Contrary to the forecasts of socialist and communist thinkers, it has been demonstrated that the long-term self-interest of individuals outweighs the collective incentives and genuine aspirations for equality and overall welfare.

According to historical records, even when they are aware of the unfairness, people are willing to accept societal injustices if there is a slight chance of achieving economic and social success. It is not feasible to achieve such an "upliftment" without subjecting or exploiting the overwhelming majority. The inherent strength of capitalism is its ability to incentivize individuals to exert maximum effort in their pursuit of upward mobility. The inherent logic of this process will ultimately reveal itself: the pursuit of economic success by each person will inevitably transform into the collective struggle for survival in the competition. In the realms of economy and society, the state of "equilibrium of fear" is swiftly established. "Lower-level" workers and managers are concerned about job loss and want to retain their positions, whereas top managers, entrepreneurs, and financiers are apprehensive about the potential decline in capital and high income and strive to increase them. All of them share a common characteristic: maximum activity, which is precisely what enhances total social well-being.

Both the lingering fear and the enticing allure of accomplishment motivate individuals to cycle as swiftly as possible. Additionally, due to the unfair distribution of the generated "cake," a small minority owns the majority of it and, despite their best efforts, is unable to distribute a sizable portion of their acquired wealth. Consequently, driven by both self-interest and the fear of lagging behind competitors, the majority of the acquired funds are promptly reinvested in fertilization efforts, with the aim of

boosting the overall level of productive forces. Inequitable, yet efficient!

When comparing the wolf laws of free capitalist competition, characterized by hyperactivity, fear, and uncertainty, with the humane models of collectivist confinement, such as self-management, market, or statistical planning, a sentimental and well-intentioned reader would likely prefer the collectivist models. Within these systems, labor and the means of production are inherently integrated, devoid of any exploitative or oppressive dynamics. There is no apprehension over unemployment or the potential financial setbacks (which are mitigated through common funds). Furthermore, the distribution of resources is equitable, ensuring just remuneration for one's effort. The magnitude of social disparities is limited, as they are directly related to the actual (productive) contribution of specific groups. There is a near absence of class conflicts. Healthcare and educational opportunities are tailored to people's capacities and societal requirements, rather than being contingent on individuals' financial resources. Solidarity funds guarantee a reasonable standard of living for even the most economically vulnerable, including those with disabilities. Existence.

What factors could potentially disturb this idealized representation of an economic system where everyone contributes to the workforce, recognizing the interconnectedness of their actions and the fundamental oneness of their interests?

Full cognizance of collective interests appears to be atypical of human nature, unless in exigent and transitory circumstances such as warfare, natural calamities, and the like. When situated in a setting characterized by selfless relationships, individuals tend to contemplate ways to reduce their actions and efforts in order to achieve fair and equitable distribution. Subsequently, they may also consider strategies to distinguish themselves from the homogeneous majority. The ideas of collectivism may appear equitable and alluring, although aligning them with the complexities of reality proves challenging (as Shakespeare would aptly remark, "Words ascend, but thoughts remain grounded"). This is likely the primary factor in socialism's global economic defeat.

In a 1960s article, Nathaniel Brandin critiques state intervention and collectivist ideologies in the United States. He poses the question: "If we were to transport members of the United American Trade Unions and three million bureaucrats back to the tenth century using a time pole, would they be capable of supplying medieval slaves with electricity, refrigerators, cars, and televisions?" Aside from stating their inability to answer, we must ascertain the factors that enabled us to do all these things. The probable solution is capitalism and unrestricted competition, while the skeptical perspectives of numerous individuals from Latin America, Africa, or Asia may partly obscure the credibility of the proposed response. However, it will become evident that their poverty has predominantly resulted from the inadequacy of the legal framework and institutions responsible for safeguarding contracts and property, both domestically and internationally.

Asserting that economists in socialist countries were oblivious to the benefits of a free market economy would be an erroneous statement. A significant number of individuals supported market relations and competition. Even in the initial phases of collectivism, there was a strong emphasis on "competition," although it differed significantly from market competition.

There have been discussions about the balance point of a socialist enterprise, which may depend on the value price, revenue price, or particular production price. One crucial concept in these debates revolved around the notion that market participants, such as rivals and producers of goods, may enhance the efficiency of the economy by anticipating market dynamics and reaching mutual agreements, thereby establishing a system based on social or state ownership. The act of negotiating and agreeing on pricing was not in conflict with the conduct of producers in the market. Instead, it was seen as a means to

expedite the formation of market equilibrium and prices, which would eventually be determined by competition, albeit with some variations. Adverse social events and negative outcomes.

If one really believes that ideal price levels can be established independent of market rivalry, then it logically follows that one should exploit the benefits of economies of scale. Consequently, if a company is founded using social or governmental capital, it is necessarily a huge corporation. Major corporations, as the primary players in the market, can easily establish a monopoly where they face no competition. This is because the all-knowing authority (represented by ministries, commissariats, commissions, boards, and often party committees) can easily determine, more effectively than the market itself, which companies are charging excessively high prices, i.e., prices that are not in line with market equilibrium.

Perhaps we should examine the underlying philosophy of this process to find an explanation for why many companies in various sectors are inclined towards negotiating and agreeing on prices, which fundamentally contradicts the fundamental principles of free competition and hinders the establishment of prices at equilibrium levels. Additionally, there is the notion that large companies, with the assistance of the state, should act as "development locomotives" around which small and medium-sized enterprises will revolve like satellites. Previously, the republics of the old RSFJ established a presence in their economic sphere by establishing a single business in each sector and in each republic, such as iron and refineries.

Furthermore, there is a prevailing notion that prices ought to be modified in accordance with wages, or at the very least, in line with the commonly accepted standard of earnings. Frequently, the media criticizes the state for the exorbitant pricing of some goods or urges it to take administrative actions to restrict those costs. Regardless, it is widely accepted that the government should intervene in price regulation. The state is pleased to engage with the populace, particularly during pre-election seasons, despite being unaware of the significant economic and long-term consequences it incurs for both the economy and the residents. Imposing administrative restrictions on the prices of infrastructure system products, such as road networks and communal services, not only results in the deterioration of these systems but also distorts price relationships. This misinformation from the market leads to inaccurate calculations of business benefits and suboptimal allocation of resources.

Conclusions

While each player in a competitive market desires to achieve a monopolistic position, referring to a corporation as a monopolist generally carries a negative implication (even the owners of such enterprises seek to conceal the fact that they have achieved their desired outcome).

Monopolies are subject to several prejudices and misconceptions. Here are a few of these misunderstandings:

- (1) Monopolies emerge naturally in the advanced stages of capitalism due to the impact of unrestricted competition (ultimately, the strongest competitor prevails in each industry);
- (2) Monopolists have the ability to set prices at their own discretion, resulting in significantly higher prices and profits compared to what would be seen in a competitive market;
- (3) When the concentration of supply exceeds a certain threshold, it inevitably leads to monopolistic behavior, characterized by inflated prices and profits;

(4) The state must assume a crucial role in combating the threat of monopolies;

(5) The presence of monopolies hinders economic growth and development by eradicating competition, suppressing entrepreneurial activities, and stifling innovation.

We will attempt to thoroughly analyze each of the above biases in a concise manner.

1. A monopoly arises when a single firm possesses a crucial resource, when the government bestows upon a company the sole privilege to manufacture a product or provide a service, and ultimately when the production expenses render one producer more effective than all others. Additional individuals.

Monopolies emerge at every phase of capitalist development. Furthermore, these entities are prone to emerge during the earliest phases (the original producer in a certain sector faces no competition initially, but competition arises later after it becomes evident that success is attainable in that domain). Nevertheless, it is indeed accurate that these monopolies are relinquished spontaneously and expeditiously.

2. Monopolies are unable to establish prices (and profits) at an excessively high level, contrary to common descriptions. Contemporary economic analysis clarified the behavior and equilibrium conditions of monopolistic and competitive producers. The equality of marginal revenue and marginal cost, which is an essential condition for profit maximization, implies that the monopolist's optimal production volume is smaller than the overall optimal production volume of competing producers. Additionally, the monopolist's equilibrium price is higher.

Naturally, this is applicable only within well-delineated parameters. Firstly, it is presumed that other producers are unable to access the market segment in which the monopolist generates greater profits. What is the reason behind my inability? There are several reasons why a company may not be able to compete with a monopolist. One reason is that the state may prohibit them from doing so in order to protect the monopolist's patent or copyright. Another reason is that they may not have access to any monopolized natural resources. Additionally, they may not be able to produce a product or service at the same low cost as the monopolist. It is worth considering whether the monopolist should be held accountable for this. Is it feasible that competitors lack sufficient capital to implement cutting-edge technology in their industry?

The monopolist is constrained in setting the monopoly price by the demand function, which represents the link between the quantity sold and the price at which it is sold. The ultimate decision he takes pertains to the magnitude of production (services). The price for the resulting production volume is established based on the demand function. The form of the marginal cost function is also a crucial factor in the decision-making process. Producers with a lower slope of the marginal cost function possess a competitive edge compared to those with a steeper slope. Does this condition benefit huge firms? Nevertheless, intuition implies that the overall marginal costs remain constant, resulting in a horizontal marginal cost function for all players. This raises the question: do larger enterprises have the lowest variable costs?

Consequently, within the paradigm, it is generally impracticable to sustain a monopoly position (along with monopoly prices) without forceful backing from other sources (such as the state!). However, the focus shifts from the issue of monopoly to the issue of state (and political) assault on the economy, which is a distinct matter and holds greater significance for transitioning countries, particularly Kosovo. Instead of contemplating the detrimental (or advantageous) consequences of monopolies.

3. The capitalist world observed the monopolistic dominance and rapid expansion of certain companies,

which appeared to have a detrimental effect on the economy, leading to a state-supported "weak laziness." This phenomenon resembled economic models seen in the Middle Ages or socialist regimes.

The Herfindahl and Hirschman (IHH) index is commonly used to quantify the level of supply concentration in a specific industry or market.

$$IHH = \sum w_i^2$$

What is the company's market share in a specific industry, given as a percentage?

The variable IHH is constrained to the interval (0, 10,000). A concentration is deemed high when the IHH (Index of Human Habitation) exceeds 1800. The concentration is considered moderate if the value of IHH falls between 1,000 and 1,800. Alternatively, the concentration may be diminished in certain instances.

The significance of concentration is frequently exaggerated in antitrust deliberations. Once a firm surpasses a specific market share, it becomes subject to antitrust measures and legislation. The concentration of specific market sectors is frequently expedited not by the expansion or consolidation of enterprises but rather by the market's shrinking due to political circumstances (such as the fragmentation of the state). This is particularly true for our country because major nations' political intentions frequently reshape its borders. Consequently, any corporation that attains a certain magnitude naturally becomes a monopolistic entity within its industry.

4. There is a commonly held misperception that the state, through its actions, may be most effective in mitigating the adverse effects of monopolistic behavior. Nevertheless, the state is primarily responsible for the creation of monopolies, as it possesses key monopolies itself. These include the monopoly on exerting legal force against its citizens, the monopoly on interpreting laws and regulations (which often lack clarity and precision), the monopoly on disseminating and interpreting information (through state-controlled media outlets and electronic platforms), and the monopoly on managing and utilizing the nation's natural resources. The state and party committees, frequently acting as a replacement for state authority, serve as the primary origin of monopoly power. Hence, the pleas to enhance the authority of the government in order to curb the monopolistic influence of corporations appear comical.

The state employs many means to combat monopolies, including antimonopoly laws, administrative pricing controls, and the nationalization of monopolistic enterprises or sectors. However, each of these solutions cannot be fully adopted without significant objections. Occasionally, the safeguarding of competition within the party-state agreement may manifest as an extremely aggressive assault on economic liberty.

The government must be urged to substantially curtail its intervention in the economy, as it frequently engages in such activities with enthusiasm. Instead, it should focus on fulfilling the crucial responsibilities necessary for a competitive economy, such as enhancing the legal framework to ensure contract security and safeguarding economic freedom, which is constantly under threat. In the absence of legal clarity and economic freedom, which refers to equal treatment under transparent laws for everyone, competition in the market cannot exist, nor can it be safeguarded.

5. Monopolies generally do not impede economic growth or diminish economic activity. Monopoly does not eradicate competition, as every company, if it has the necessary means, desires to enter the monopoly market, which is more appealing owing to the higher prices it offers. The state can undermine free competition by employing violent methods to safeguard a monopolistic producer or by using violence to topple the monopolist and protect minor producers.

The strong critique overlooks the positive impacts of monopolies on economic development. The aggregation of capital enables the exploitation of economies of scale. In addition, contemporary technology, while enabling significant cost reductions per unit of output (or service), necessitates substantial upfront financial inputs, which are typically only feasible for major corporations (such as for research and development, testing, and market expansion).

Furthermore, it can be readily demonstrated that monopoly prices result in the transfer of consumer surplus to the producer, namely within the sector of the economy. The money is allocated for investment rather than expenditure (in the public sector). Is it imperative to elucidate the influence of savings and investment on the overall trajectory of economic growth and development?

Microsoft, a contemporary monopoly, exemplifies a leading firm in technical advancement, with substantial investments in research and development and a remarkable capacity for innovation. Is it plausible that other small companies (whose combined capital would be equivalent to that of MS) might obtain comparable levels of funding? Is their combined effect similar to that of MS?

Undoubtedly, when doing a thorough examination of the functioning of monopolistic enterprises, it is crucial not to disregard the negative aspects, which we shall reiterate:

The equilibrium of a monopoly producer is characterized by a lower level of output volume and services, as well as a higher price level, in comparison to a competitive producer. When trying to move the consumer demand curve towards the right, monopolists frequently encounter significant expenses related to propaganda, lobbying, and other factors that can help achieve this objective. These expenses frequently out to be socially unwarranted.

Recommendation

To conclude, we will initially present two opposing yet valid viewpoints:

Monopolies are prevalent in the contemporary capitalist economy, arising from advancements not just in finance and economics but also in technology. Given that a single company typically controls the major economic sectors, one could argue that our world is characterized by monopolies.

Conversely, it is challenging to locate corporations that possess genuine monopolistic authority. In the contemporary landscape of consumerism, diverse commodities from different industries have become readily interchangeable, leading to intense competition among individuals.

The geographical concentration of our country's market has led certain corporations, such as those in the metallurgy industry, to attain a monopoly position. Furthermore, numerous organizations that attempt to leverage the advantages of economies of scale may quickly find themselves in a monopolistic position as a result of their expansion.

Despite common misconceptions, monopolies possess both negative and positive attributes. In addition to drawbacks such as high pricing and limited production, monopolies also benefit from economies of scale, synergistic effects, the transfer of consumer surplus to producers, and increased investments in research and development.

The user's text is a bullet point. Anticipating the state, which is an established and dominant monopolist, to effectively safeguard free competition by further increasing its already considerable economic authority is challenging. In order to safeguard competition, rather than pursuing monopolists, which may appear to be a diversionary tactic, the government should prioritize activities that are crucial for competition protection: enhancing the legal framework while concurrently reducing state intervention

in the economy. Subjects (individuals engaged in a competitive conflict) must experience a sense of equality under the jurisdiction of the law.

The primary obstacle to the growth of the market economy and competition in Kosovo is not the monopolistic control of enterprises in certain sectors but rather the full domination of the economy by political interests, namely those of political parties. The ideology of the controlled economy continues to prevail in the attitude of politicians (as well as ordinary citizens), who rely on the government for intervention (and assistance) rather than advocating for increased economic liberty for entrepreneurs, financiers, and workers.

References

1. Sermaxhaj, S., Arifi, F., Alaj, I., & Selimi, M. (2022, October 1). The Impact of Morphological Characteristics and Motoric Skills in Young Football Players' Selection. *Sport Mont*, 20(3), 35–39. <https://doi.org/10.26773/smj.221006>
2. Fejza, V., Livoreka, R., & Bajrami, H. (2017). ANALYZING CONSUMER BEHAVIOR IN BANKING SECTOR OF KOSOVO. *Eurasian Journal of Business and Management*, 5(4), 33–48. <https://doi.org/10.15604/ejbm.2017.05.04.004>
3. Lllagjevic-Govori, A., Tahiraj, E., Llagjaj, D., Grajqevci, F., & Shkodra, A. (2019, February 1). Organizing Manage of International Half Marathon “Run for Peace and Tolerance.” *Sport Mont*, 17(1), 97–100. <https://doi.org/10.26773/smj.190219>
4. Hundozi, Z., Ibishi, N., Jashari, F., Rrustemi, J., & Gjikolli, B. (2016, December 16). Superior Sagittal Sinus Thrombosis Presenting with Hallucinations in the Puerperium: A Case Report. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(4), 294–297. [https://doi.org/10.21103/article6\(4\)_cr2](https://doi.org/10.21103/article6(4)_cr2)
5. Hoti, A., Alshiqi - Bekteshi, S., & Livoreka, B. (2014, June 1). Performance of Foreign Banks Operating in Kosovo – ProCredit Bank Kosovo - Raiffeisen Bank Kosovo & NLB Prishtina. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.5901/ajis.2014.v3n2p57>
6. Hoxha, R., Hoti, H., & Kurhasku, E. G. (2016, May 5). Opportunities for Foreign Investments in the Economy of Kosovo. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2016.v7n3p185>
7. Pula, F. (2015, May 1). Business Orientated to Women and Her Impact on Economy (Case Kosovo). *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2015.v6n3s1p43>
8. Cox, R., & Axworthy, L. (2000, January). Correspondence: The Crisis in Kosovo. *Studies in Political Economy*, 63(1), 133–152. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19187033.2000.11675236>
9. Local economy advisory board. (1987, August). *Local Economy: The Journal of the Local Economy Policy Unit*, 2(2), np-np. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02690948708725887>
10. Sayer, A. (2000, January). Moral Economy and Political Economy. *Studies in Political Economy*, 61(1), 79–103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19187033.2000.11675254>
11. Griffith, R., Nesheim, L., & O'Connell, M. (2018, March). Income effects and the welfare consequences of tax in differentiated product oligopoly. *Quantitative Economics*, 9(1), 305–341. <https://doi.org/10.3982/qe583>

12. GS, R. (2020, August 19). Opioid Oligopoly and the Seven Deadly Sins (007). *Clinical Research Notes*, 1(3), 01–05. <https://doi.org/10.31579/2690-8816/026>
13. Naya, J. M. (2011, August 21). Mixed oligopoly, endogenous timing and mergers. *International Journal of Economic Theory*, 7(3), 283–291. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1742-7363.2011.00164.x>
14. Duller, C. (2016, April 3). Die österreichische private Krankenversicherung - Ein Monopol? *Austrian Journal of Statistics*, 34(4). <https://doi.org/10.17713/ajs.v34i4.422>
15. Fladberg, L. (1970, January 1). Monopol eller sjakk (matt)? *Prismet*, 2, 119–128. <https://doi.org/10.5617/pri.4662>
16. Schuhmacher. (2010, October). Auf der Ebene eines Bundeslands bestehendes staatliches Monopol auf die Veranstaltung von Sportwetten; Unvereinbarkeit der ein solches Monopol betreffenden Regelung mit dem dt Grundgesetz; Zulässigkeit und eventuelle Voraussetzungen einer Übergangszeit. *Wirtschaftsrechtliche Blätter*, 24(10), 521–525. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00718-010-1726-y>
17. Labouvie, E. (1995, January). Frauen im Monopol- und Großhandel. *L'Homme*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.7767/lhomme.1995.6.1.46>
18. Vom Monopol zum Markt? (1993). *Neue Kriminalpolitik*, 5(2), 30–31. <https://doi.org/10.5771/0934-9200-1993-2-30> books?hl=tr&lr=&id=C6HfAgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR1&dq=Promoting+health+and+emotional+wellbeing+in+your+classroom.+ (5.+Basketball%20C4%B1).+USA:+Jones+and+Bartlett+Publishers.&ots=ESMPoZZJt&sig=rjg7vkFZOejal1lz_AEPdr_5FcU&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Promoting%20health%20and%20emotional%20wellbeing%20in%20your%20classroom.%20(5.%20Basketball%20C4%B1).%20USA%3A%20Jones%20and%20Bartlett%20Publishers.&f=false adresinden erişildi.
19. Sağır, A., Özdemir, M., Erden, S., Günay, A., & Apalak, G. (2019). Risk toplumunda yeni bir boyut olarak dijitalleşen gündelik hayat: bilgisayar oyunlarının ortaokul öğrencileri üzerine etkisi (Mavi Balina ve Momo Örneği), *TİHEK*, 4-5, 59-72.
20. Sırakaya, M. ve Seferoğlu, S. S. (2018). Çocukların çevrim-içi ortamlarda karşılaştıkları riskler ve güvenli internet kullanımı. (Eğitim teknolojileri okumaları içinde 185-202). TOJET, Adapazarı.
21. Söğütlüler, T., & Başer, E. (2023). Dijital Çağda Ebeveyn Olmak: Çocuk İzleyiciler ve Ekrandaki Şiddet Üzerine Bir Araştırma. *TRT Akademi*, 08(19), 814-845. <https://doi.org/10.37679/trta.1328304>
22. TCK (2004). Türk Ceza Kanunu. <https://www.mevzuat.gov.tr/MevzuatMetin/1.5.5237.pdf> adresinden erişildi.
23. TÜİK, (2021). Çocuklarda Bilişim Teknolojileri Kullanım Araştırması, <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Cocuklarda-Bilisim-Teknolojileri-Kullanim-Arastirmasi-2021-41132#:~:text=Bilgisayar%20kulland%C4%B1%C4%9F%C4%B1n%C4%B1%20belirten%20%C3%A7ocuklar%C4%B1n%20ya%C5%9F,i%20bilgisayar%20kulland%C4%B1%C4%9F%C4%B1n%C4%B1%20beyan%20etti.&text=Bilgisayar%20kullanan%206%2D15%20ya%C5%9F,ile%20tablet%20bilgisayar%20kulland%C4%B1%C4%9F%C4%B1%20g%C3%B6r%C3%BCld%C3%BC>
24. UNICEF, (2017). Dünya çocuklarının durumu: Dijital bir dünyada çocuklar. <https://www.unicef.org/turkey/media/4291/file/D%C3%BCnya%20%C3%87ocuklar%C4%B1n%C4%B1n%20>

Durumu%202017:%20Dijital%20bir%20D%C3%BCnyada%20%C3%87ocuklar.pdf adresinden erişildi.

25. Ünal, S., & Yıldız, F. (2020). Dijital risk toplumunda meydan okuma videoları ve çocuklar: Adana’da ortaöğretim öğrencilerine yönelik bir alan araştırmasından bulgular. *Selçuk İletişim Dergisi*, 13(1), 197-226.
26. Valcke, M., Bonte , S., De Wever , B., & Rots , I. (2010). Internet parenting styles and the impact on Internet use of primary school children. *Computers & Education*, 55(2), 454- 464. https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360131510000436?casa_token=PnBrk7il8D0AAAAA:ZosD4dZXVm5BbZ6ZOxpzZpslKdo_9-OWYD59IxTODIp3yFFO9lovp4ZsB3Wuj2szcQDbmvifBg adresinden erişildi.
27. Yıldırım, A., & Şimşek, H. (2008). *Sosyal Bilimlerde Nitel Araştırma Yöntemleri*. Ankara: Seçkin Yayıncılık.
28. Yiğit Açıkgöz, F., & Yalman, A. (2018). Dijital Oyunların Çocukların Kişilik ve Davranışları Üzerinde Etkisi: Gta 5 Oyunu Örneği. *Akdeniz Üniversitesi İletişim Fakültesi Dergisi*(29. Özel Sayısı), 163-180. <https://doi.org/10.31123/akil.454283>
29. Yiğit, N., & Alat, K. (2022). Erken Çocukluk Dönemindeki Çocukların Dijital Oyun Oynama Alışkanlıklarına İlişkin Anne/Baba Görüşleri. *E-Kafkas Journal of Educational Research*, 9(3), 1026-1052. <https://doi.org/10.30900/kafkasegt.1140899>
30. Warden, D. (2005). The prevention of child sexual abuse. (Child safety: Problem and prevention from preschool to adolescence içinde 122-133). London: Routledge. https://www.jstor.org/stable/1602531?casa_token=785PUp5XdeEAAAAA%3Art2DvaaOO_mnBXzdnngWRr-nYZeFGZS-BM8mZT09kBrhECa06qLLC8E4tHqyWMbH3Wd3cowKS5APjJvWiTwfCByXgnsuWi3I_pNZ-SjXOjD8_m4I7xac&seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents adresinden erişildi.